

The limit between plated and shell behaviour on polygonal cross-sections

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ABSTRACT

Regular closed-polygon sections (RCPS) are a cost-efficient alternative to circular hollow sections, widely used for telecommunication towers, lighting and overhead electrical lines, having a potential as wind towers. Current regulations cover only mild steels and provide limited knowledge on the failure mechanisms or the influence of initial imperfections. This paper summarises the findings of an RFCS funded study (RFSR-CT- 2015-00021) on short polygonal members investigating whether plate or shell-theory would be best fit for a certain RCPS. The study was performed through extended numerical and laboratory tests. A formula is proposed describing the limit for the failure-mode shift of an RCPS, assisting the design by designating the appropriate Eurocode to be considered.

Keywords: polygonal sections, High-strength steel, plate buckling, shell buckling

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Motivation

The resistance to compression for a typical plated cross-section of high local slenderness is limited by plate buckling failure. For a closed profile, such as a square hollow section (SHS), the plate width of each side and consequently the plate slenderness can be reduced by introducing additional vertices to the cross-section, producing regular closed polygonal sections (RCPS) of increasing order (number of vertices).

Assuming the edges can effectively support the sides, one could increase the cross-section's resistance up to the plastic limit by indefinitely increasing the polygon order as illustrated by the region B of *Fig. 1*.

Fig. 1. Resistance of RCPS of constant area $A_p = 1e4$ mm², as calculated by Eurocodes, assuming facets as simply supported plates, ignoring distortional buckling mode. a) 3m long, b) 5m long. Regions: A) plastic limit B) plate buckling C) flexural buckling.

The above assumption is clearly false as the edges become increasingly obtuse and naturally become unable to support the plates. From that limit, the cross-section cannot be thought of as a collection of simply supported plates and thus, plate theory is inadequate for predicting the compressive resistance.

It can be thought of as the cross-section approaches a cylinder by the introduction of additional vertices. It follows logically that shell theory and the corresponding design formulas could be applicable beyond the limit which plate behaviour becomes invalid.

The present paper presents the findings of a research programme investigating the limit between plate and shell behaviour, through numerical simulations and laboratory experiments within the context of the design procedures of the Eurocodes.

1.2 Applications

Polygonal profiles are widely used as masts in several applications. Such structures can be commonly found as lighting poles of small (streetlights, traffic signals) or larger scale (stadium lighting, airports).

Another application is electrical overhead lines. RCPS profiles can be found supporting power-grid lines as well as train power lines. A particular advantage for the latter case is the reduced footprint, allowing them to be placed between the train lines.

Particularly interesting is a common friction-connection type referred as “slip joint”, where two parts of a pole fit conically into each other, greatly simplifying erection. This connection is described in (1).

In addition, such profiles have a great potential in wind tower applications, as they minimize the hoop imperfections introduced by the circumferential welds on traditionally manufactured tubular towers.

1.3 Regulatory framework

The design of polygonal pylons is covered in (1). This norm covers cross-sections with six and up to 18 sides. Cross-section classification rules are given which coincide with the plate class limits and effective area of (2, 3). The present study considers the applicability of (4) for higher order polygons. Of relevance is the framework for thin-walled structures (5), as it provides more detailed description of the properties of cold-formed edges.

1.4 Literature review

Bulson (6) tested 43 short polygonal columns of 4 to 40 sides. He suggested the limit of plated behaviour to $n_v = 18$ with good agreement to the experimental results. Focused on rocket science, all specimens were of very high plate slenderness, beyond the scope of civil engineering applications.

Buckling curves for RCPS of four, five, six and of higher orders were proposed by Avent and Robinson (7), by solving the differential equations with finite Fourier series while Kurt and Johnson (8) included initial imperfections following the same methodology. The initial imperfections were considered only on the individual facets (no distortional imperfections).

RCPS were later studied by Aoki, Migita and Fukumoto with two papers (9, 10). Experiments of specimens of four to eight sides and varying lengths were presented. An empirical equation was proposed based on the observations. The study was expanded with numerical analyses with plate-affine imperfections, including all even sided RCPSs from 4 to 24 sides, plus the five and seven sided ones, and concluded an updated version of the earlier resistance formula. It was also observed that, though failure followed the imperfection shape, some different modes occurred for higher order polygons, indicating distortional buckling. A limit of 24 sides for the mode change was mentioned.

Teng et al. (11) investigated RCPS with four to eight sides using the finite strip method to obtain the elastic critical load under combined compression and bending.

An experimental study of short columns of orders 8, 12 and 16 performed by Godat et al. (12), including imperfection measurements, demonstrated the two dominant failure modes of plated and

cylindrical (distortional) nature. One specimen with as few as 12 sides failed in a distortional manner, resembling the elephant-foot shape close to the support. A formula based on experimental results was proposed for the RCPSs resistance.

Gonçalves and Camotim (13–16) studied the elastic stability of RCPS using the Generalised Beam Theory (GBT) and modal decomposition. The study explored linear and non-linear cases of compression, bending and torsion.

Sabau (17) performed a numerical investigation on RCPS of various lengths, with global slenderness up to $\lambda=1.2$ and evaluated the adequacy of the buckling curves of (2).

The present paper includes parts of an extended numerical and experimental study on the plate and distortional buckling modes of RCPS, presented in depth in (18). A statistical analysis of the experiments found in literature is presented in (19).

2 GEOMETRY AND IMPERFECTIONS

2.1 The geometry of RCPS

For reasons of clarity, it is useful to describe the basic geometric properties and definitions for an RCPS. A regular polygon can be described by its radius r_p (vertex to centre distance) and the order n_v (number of vertices). The angle between a radius and an adjacent apothem is denoted as θ .

Accounting for the radius of the bent corners r_b , the perimeter of an RCPS measured at the mid-thickness of the plate, p_p , is given by:

$$p_p = n_v \cdot b_f + 2\pi \cdot r_b \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2. Basic geometric properties of an RCPS.

Expressing the bending radius of the edges in relation to the thickness, $r_b=a_b \cdot t$, the cross-sectional area of an RCPS is given as:

$$A_p = 2t \cdot (n_v r_p \sin \theta - n_v a_b t \tan \theta + \pi a_b t) \quad (2)$$

2.2 Equivalent cylinder

To allow for comparison between RCPS of different order, the concept of an equivalent cylinder is introduced.

The equivalent cylinder to an RCPS is one with same cross-sectional area and thickness. Equating the expressions of cross-sectional areas of the two, the radius of an equivalent cylinder is calculated as:

$$r_c = \frac{n_v}{\pi} (r_p \sin \theta - a_b t \tan \theta) + a_b t \quad (3)$$

The profiles are analysed in terms of the plate slenderness of the facets p_c , as defined in (2).

$$p_c = b_f / \varepsilon t \quad (4)$$

Finally, the equivalent cylinder of an RCPS of given order n_v and plate slenderness p_c , which are two of the main parameters of the present study, is given as:

$$r_c = t \left(\frac{n_v p_c \varepsilon}{2\pi} + a_b \right) \quad (5)$$

2.3 Resistance

Throughout the study, the RCPSs are analysed for their expected resistance according to (2) as well as the respective codes for slender plates and cylinders (3) and (4). Where local buckling is relevant (class 4), the resistance is calculated as in *Eq. (6)* for plates and *Eq. (7)* for shells.

$$N_{Rd,plt} = \frac{A_{eff} f_y}{\gamma_{M0}} \quad (6)$$

$$N_{Rd,shl} = A \sigma_{x,Rd} \quad (7)$$

where $\sigma_{x,Rd} = \frac{\sigma_{x,Rk}}{\gamma_{M1}}$

2.4 Imperfections

For the application of initial imperfections to the FE models, as well as for the assessment of the test specimens, a consistent geometric description is required. An analytical description of the imperfect shape helps categorising the actual failure mechanism of the FE analyses.

Imperfections are constructed by imposing sinusoidal functions of alternating frequencies and amplitudes on the perfect geometry. These can be best described on the unfolded flat pattern of the RCPS. By choosing wavelength, shapes corresponding to plate imperfections (half-wavelength equal to facet width), or general shell imperfections (half-wavelength greater than the facet's width) can be produced. By shell-imperfections are described all possible shapes for which dimples ignore the edges and stretch, or “spillover” to two or more consecutive facets.

A natural constraint is imposed by the requirement for continuity and differentiability along the circumference and the length of the specimen. For example, introducing plate-like imperfections to an even-sided polygon, leads to two consecutive sides having both troughs or crests (i.e., displaced inwards or outwards), thus violating the differentiability constraint. This problem is overcome by windowing the wave function, as depicted in *Fig. 3*. This technique, often used in signal processing for the exact same purpose, is used to introduce imperfections in the FE models as well as for the assessment of the test-specimens after 3D scanning their geometry. This results in a shape where one side of the RCPS is near perfect while the other side hosts maximum imperfections.

Fig. 3. Assumed imperfections a) plate-like; b) double spillover.

For consistency throughout the calculations, the amplitude of imperfections is assessed based shell-theory, as described in (4). Therein, three fabrication classes (A, B and C) are described, with respective maximum deviations from the perfect geometry.

3 NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

3.1 Parametric study

An extended parametric study of geometric and material non-linear FE analyses with imperfections (GMNIA) was performed, designed to investigate the space where the change in failure mode was expected. A full factorial matrix of the considered key variables was constructed, as described in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Parametric matrix for FEM.

Dimension	Set of values	Number of values
Number of vertices, n_v	4 to 49	46
Plate slenderness, p_c	27 to 60 in steps of 3	12
Material model	S355, S700	2
Imperfection amplitude (as of fabrication class)	fcA, fcB, fcC	3
Imperfection type	Plate, various distortional modes	4

For just one execution, the Cartesian product of the parameters results in a sum of 13248 individual GMNIA models. To deal with this number of models, the entire process, from modelling to analyses and postprocessing was automated with the help of Python, Fortran, and the equivalent API of Abaqus CAE. The study was entirely executed in a cluster computer available through the Swedish National Infrastructure for Computing (SNIC), utilising parallel execution to decrease the overall solving time.

3.2 FE results

From the initial set of four imperfection shapes, namely 1) plate-like 2) single spillover 3) double spillover 4) multiple spillover, the cases of plate and double spillover (dimples stretching over two facets as in *Fig. 3-b*) yielded consistently the lowest results, see *Fig. 4*. It was also observed that the deformed shape at failure was following the shape of the imperfections.

Fig. 4. Ratio σ_{GMNIA}/f_y for different imperfection patterns (S355, fab. Class A).

Based on the observations above, the two imperfection shapes were used to obtain resistance results for the two failure types (plate and distortional or shell-like buckling).

Taking the minimum between the resulted resistance from models with plate-like imperfections and distortional (double spillover), it becomes apparent that two distinct regions are formed. As

depicted in Fig. 5. RCPS of lower order present a lower resistance when they follow a plate-like failure, while distortional types of failure lead to minimum resistance for higher order polygons, as expected.

Interestingly, the limit between the two regions depends also on the plate slenderness as well as the magnitude of imperfections and the yield stress. It is also observed that a general limit to 18 corners, as provisioned by (1) can become unsafe for high strength steels and large imperfections (fabrication class B and C).

Fig. 5. Ratio $\sigma_{\text{GMNIA},\text{min}}/f_y$ between models with plate and double spillover imperfections. The dashed line designates the border between critical plate (left region) and critical shell (right region) resistance. The dotted line, $n_v=18$, designate the limit adopted by EN 50341.

3.3 Verification against Eurocodes

The resulted resistance from the GMNIA is compared to the predicted resistance of the Eurocode formulas. The results, depicted in Fig. 6, show that (4) gives a resistance prediction on the safe side within its corresponding region (right side of the limit line). While (3) seems to overestimate the resistance over its corresponding region (left side of the limit line), it does so in a very consistent manner, designating that the failure mechanism is correctly described by the theory. The overestimation is a result of the imperfection magnitude, which stems from the fabrication classes of (4) instead of (3).

Fig. 6. Minimum resulted FEM resistance with alternating imperfections compared to Eurocode resistance calculations a) ratio $N_{GMNIA,min}/N_{b,Rd,plt}$ (EN 1993-1-5) b) ratio $N_{GMNIA,min}/N_{b,Rd,shl}$ (EN 1993-1-6).

4 EXPERIMENTS

A set of nine specimens were fabricated and tested under pure compression. The specimens were designed to span over the critical region where the failure mode change was expected.

The specimen matrix, shown in Fig. 7 consisted RCPS of three orders {16, 20, 24} with plate slenderness of $b_f/(\epsilon \cdot t) = \{30, 40, 50\}$.

All specimens were short, $l=700$ mm, with flexural slenderness well below the squash limit of $\lambda=0.2$. To ensure a pure compression stress state, cylindrical bearings were placed on each end. All specimens were manufactured out of two different steel plates, both S700 MC.

Initial geometrical imperfections were measured by 3D scanning the specimens and analysing all individual facets with 2D FFT to quantify the deformations in terms of wavelengths and amplitudes. Assessment according to (4) placed all specimen in fabrication class A.

After testing, the deformed specimens were 3D scanned again, to capture the resulted buckled shape. The actual failure modes showed good correlation with the expectations from the numerical investigation.

All specimens with low slenderness where plate buckling was not critical, presented a type of elephant foot failure, deforming both facets and edges.

The specimens with higher slenderness presented the corresponding failure-modes, with SP3 demonstrating a clear plate-buckling failure, while specimen 6 and 9 undergoing a near perfect double-spillover failure.

Specimens of intermediate slenderness followed the same pattern only slightly less obvious. The low order specimen, SP2 (hexadecagon), showed a plate buckling failure with all facets bulged outwards, though the edges remained almost straight.

Fig. 8. Average stress-strain curves of the nine experiments.

Fig. 9. 3D scanned models of the deformed specimens after testing.

Fig. 7. Specimen matrix plotted together with the borders of the different expected failure modes as resulted by FEM.

Table 2. Specimen properties.

	SP1	SP2	SP3	SP4	SP5	SP6	SP7	SP8	SP9
n_v	16	26	16	20	202	20	24	24	24
p_c	30	40	50	30	40	50	30	40	50
t , [mm]	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	2	2
r_c , [mm]	142	186	230	175	230	190	108	183	227

5 ANALYSIS

The limit borders between the two regions of critical plate and shell behaviour, as resulted by the FE analyses and validated by the experiments, were approximated with simplified straight lines.

Fig. 10. Failure-mode change borders and the proposed linear approximations

The proposed limits can aid the design of RCPS in conjunction with the Eurocodes, by designating which framework is appropriate. The limits can be expressed in terms of the RCPS order, n_v , using the proposed Eq. (8).

$$\begin{aligned} n_v \leq \kappa & \quad \text{Design acc. to EN 1993-1-5} \\ n_v > \kappa & \quad \text{Design acc. to EN 1993-1-6} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa &= \xi + \frac{p_c - 27}{\zeta}, \quad 27 \leq p_c \leq 60 \\ \zeta &= \begin{cases} 4.1, & \text{for fab. class A} \\ 7.4, & \text{for fab. class B} \\ 34.2, & \text{for fab. class C} \end{cases} \\ \xi &= 24 - 0.02 f_y, \quad \text{for } f_y \leq 700 \text{ MPa} \end{aligned}$$

6 CONCLUSIONS

- The limit of 18 vertices (1) appears correct for S235, S355.
- For HSS with larger imperfections, the limit of 18 vertices can be unsafe.
- An equation is proposed for the choice of a design method using (3) or (4) for RCPSs.

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